

ISic1256

I.Sicily inscription 1256

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Seen by Campagna 2005-03-30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. θεαῖς
2. ἀγναῖς
3. χαριστή
4. ριον
5. Λ(ούκιος) · Μάλιος
6. Ἑρμῆς
7. ῥέκτας

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492862

EDCS 39101624

PHI 140744

Bibliography

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Photo L. Campagna 2005-03-31